

STRAIN MAPPING OF HIGH PERFORMANCE FIBRES IN TEXTILE ARCHITECTURES

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SUMMARY

This paper investigates the influence of interlacing architectures on micro- and meso-scale strain distribution in high performance fibres using Raman spectroscopy. In the present study Vectran fibre was used as a reinforcement to produce single layer plain-weave composite lamina. Infrared Raman spectroscopy has been used to investigate the deformation behaviour of the Vectran fibres and in this study the same technique extended to measure the deformation behaviour of the Vectran fibres within the composite lamina. Local fibre strain and strain mapping for the representative unit cell of plain weave composite are investigated and it's found that the stresses are concentrated at the edges of the unit cell due to the interlacing mechanism.

Keywords: Raman Spectroscopy, Textile architectures, strain distribution, interface, composites

INTRODUCTION

High performance fibres such as Kevlar, PBO and Vectran are used in a number of advanced applications such as body armour, rigid armour plates, structural composites and deployable space systems. These fibres, normally supplied as multi-filament yarns, are converted into fabrics using a variety of interlacement architectures Fig. 1. The resulting fabrics may be used in the dry form in a number of applications such as body armour. Protective coating or lamination may be used for other applications including deployable space structures. The detailed deformation of woven composite are investigated by using Raman spectroscopy for many high performance fibres and proved to be a good tool to follow the micro deformation of the reinforcing fibres in woven composites [1].

Figure 1: Textile architectures

Vectran is a wholly-aromatic liquid crystal polyester fibre that has some unique properties [2]. Vectran fibre is known for its strength, rigidity, abrasion and moisture resistance, and property retention over a broad range of temperature and chemical environments [2, 3, and 4]. One of the first trials to use Raman spectroscopy to investigate the deformation behaviour of thermotropic aromatic copolyesters was undertaken by Ward and Young [5]. Near infrared (INR) Raman was used to investigate thermotropic aromatic copolyesters fibres deformation behaviour, as very high levels of fluorescence were formed using visible wavelength laser. The peak position shifts to a lower wavenumber with stress or strain following tensile deformation. Tanaka [5] reported that the developed bumper shields made with using Vectran fibres has good impact resistance. Takano *et al* [7] reported that the main difficulty in predictive modelling of micro-strain fields in textile composites is the lack of experimental techniques for validation. Full-field techniques such as speckle pattern interferometry, digital image correlation, photo stress and Moiré techniques have the potential to detect the strain gradients. However, these techniques measure the laminate surface strains rather than local strains in the fibre direction. In this work, Raman spectroscopy has been employed to measure local strains in fibres, with a gauge length of 2 μ m. Fibre strains were determined from the Raman band shift. Alternately, thermoplastic or thermoset resins are used as matrix materials for producing composites for rigid armour and other structural applications. In textile architectures, there exists an intermediate scale, generally referred to as meso-scale, due to the interlacement of the fibre bundles. The main objectives of this work were two-fold;

- a) To assess the influence of interlacement architecture (plain-weave) on the meso-scale strain distribution.
- b) To assess the influence of matrix on micro-scale (fibre-fibre interface) and meso-scale strain distribution.

2. Experimental procedure

2-1 Materials

A Single-ply plain-weave epoxy lamina with a commercial grade of Vectran (thermotropic aromatic copolyester) fibres was employed as reinforcement in this study. The Vectran plain weave fabric and multifilament tow was supplied by Kubota Research Associates, Inc. The material specifications are given in Table 1. The Vectran/epoxy composite laminate was produced using vacuum assisted infusion process in room temperature. The reinforcement, a plain weave fabric is shown in Fig 2.

Table 1 Details of the Vectran/epoxy woven lamina

Fibre	Fabric	Composite lamina
Tow linear density = 1433.7 denier Fibre diameter = 26.83 \pm 1.7 Fibre failure strain = 3.07 \pm 0.23 % Tensile strength = 3.87 \pm 0.36 Gpa Young's modulus = 126.3 \pm 11.65 Gpa	Structure: Plain weave Ends/inch = 12.5/inch Picks/inch = 12.5/inch Areal density = 163.017g/m ²	Type of resin Epoxy Areal density = 341.65g/m ² Fabric volume fraction = 0.437 Epoxy volume fraction = 0.563

2-2 Fibre Testing:

Individual fibres were placed on paper window cards using super-glue as shown in Fig. 3. After curing completely (24 hours in standard Lab. atmosphere), the paper card was clamped by two grips in an Instron (model 1122) machine and the edges of card was burned carefully. A 5 N load cell was used and measurements were made using 5 N full-scale deflection with a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Gauge lengths of 50 mm was employed using paper window cards and 30 specimens were tested. The average values of fibre diameter (30 measurements) measured using SEM (calibrated with standard mesh) was used to calculate the fibre stresses. All tests were carried out at a temperature of 20 ± 1 °C and relative humidity of 50 ± 5 %.

2-3 Specimen Preparation

The specimens for mechanical testing were cut from the moulded Vectran/epoxy woven laminate using special cutters. The dimensions of the specimens were $90 \times 16 \times 0.35$ mm³ (length x width x thickness). Aluminium tabs were attached onto each specimen using super-glue adhesive in order to distribute the applied load uniformly. A resistance strain gauge with dimensions 11×4 mm², with gauge factor 2.08, was glued onto the surface of specimen to record the variation of overall lamina surface strain. The specimen preparation is illustrated schematically in Fig.4.

Fig.2 Photography of plain weave fabric.

Fig.4. Illustration of specimen preparation

Fig.3 Specimen for the single-fibre mechanical test.

Fig.5 Micrograph of the cross-sectional area of Vectran plain weave composite

The internal structure of the Vectran/epoxy samples investigated using optical microscope. The composite lamina was sectioned and embedded within a fast cured polyester resin, which was allowed to cure for three hours in room temperature. Then the moulded samples were ground and polished using a Struers Universal Polisher. The detailed cross-sectional geometry of the defined cell of the plain weave laminae is

represented in Fig. 5. Strain mapping has been developed by identifying certain paths to measure the local fibre strain. These paths cover the whole area of the unit cell which is represented in Fig's. 6, 7. Due to the symmetry of the unit cell some paths were scanned only for their half length. Fig. 7 shows the scanned paths, each line represents a scanning path; and the arrows denote the direction of external loading.

Fig.6 Schematically illustration of 1D representative unit cell of plain weave.

Fig.7 Schematically illustration of the measuring paths P1, P2 and P3 across the filling and P4, P5 along the filling.

2-4 Raman Spectra

Raman spectra were obtained from single fibres using a Renishaw 1000 Raman system with 830 nm invisible laser beam of a 4.5 mW Infrared laser focused to at $\sim 2\mu\text{m}$ diameter spot on the surface of the fibre through a microscope with a x50 objective lens. For single fibre deformation a highly sensitive charged-coupled device (CCD) camera was used to collect Raman spectra using an exposure time of 3 s and 10 accumulations. While spectra were been collected from plain weave composite lamina at the same time of exposure and number of accumulations, the laser power for each spectrum was increased to 33.2 mW, therefore to improve signal quality. The data were then collected and stored using a computer. A tensile rig fitted with 250 g load cell was used to deform single fibres, while a 'Minimat' miniature tensile tester with a maximum load capacity of 1 kN was used to deform composite specimen. Both Minimat and fibre tensile rig were made by Polymer Laboratories, UK. They were placed on the microscope stage of the Raman spectrometer. Raman spectra were obtained at different levels of applied stress. The stress rig is shown schematically in Fig's8, 9. The strain was determined from the micrometer displacement.

3- Results and discussion

3-1 Fibre testing

A typical spectrum obtained from the Vectran fibres at two different strain levels is given in Fig. 10. The Raman band at 1602 cm^{-1} obtained from the Vectran fibre is due to stretch in the phenyl ring [3]. It was used to follow the deformation behaviour because these bands are intense and well-defined for the Vectran [3]. It can be seen that the peak position shifts to a lower wave number under the application of tensile deformation, the exact band shift rate out of testing 30 fibres were $4.7\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%\text{strain}$. The deformation of the Vectran fibres carried out using the stressing rig shown in Fig. 8 that enables the tensile deformation of the fibres to be studied.

Fig.8 Illustration of 'Minimat' strain rig

Fig.9 Schematic diagram of the stressing rig. The digital numbers indicate the load applied.

Fig.10 Raman spectra of the 1602 band for Vectran fibre obtained at 0 and 2.0 % tensile strain

Fig.11 The dependence of the peak position of the 1602 cm-1 Raman band for Vectran subjected to a tensile stress.

Fig. 11 shows the shift in peak position of 1602 cm^{-1} for the Vectran fibres, upon the application of tension. It is shown that the peak position of the Raman band for Vectran fibres is sensitive to the strain and shifting to lower wavenumber in tension. It was also found that the Raman band shift rate (\equiv slope of line in Fig. 11) is approximately linear. The surface morphology of the Vectran fibres is shown in Fig.13. It can be seen that the surfaces of the Vectran fibres are relatively smooth.

The stress-strain curve for single fibre used to produce the Vectran composite lamina tested with a gauge length of 50 mm is shown in Fig.12. The mechanical properties of both Vectran fibres and composite laminae are listed in Table 1.

3-2 Strain Mapping

3-2-1 One dimensional (1D) strain distribution

The deformation process of woven fabric composite is thought to be complex and to some extent it is difficult to be fully predictable, this related to the complicated microstructure of woven fabric composites [8-9]. The detailed deformation of Vectran/epoxy plain weave composite are investigated by using Raman spectroscopy, which is proved to be a good tool to follow the micro deformation of the fibres reinforcement for many high performance fibres [10-13].

Fig.12 Stress-strain curves for Vectran fibres at gauge length of 50 mm

Fig.13 Scanning electron micrograph of Vectran fibre

Fig.14 1D fibre strain mapping across the filling for Vectran/epoxy composite

Fig.15 1D fibre strain mapping along the filling for Vectran/epoxy composite

Figures (14-15) show the one dimension fibre strain distributions obtained from point-to-point mapping along the centre of filling and across the filling directions that are parallel and perpendicular to the direction of the applied force for the Vectran/epoxy composite,

respectively. It can be seen from one dimensional strain mapping that the fibre strain increases as the overall composite strain increases. Also, it should be noted that the lowest fibre strain occurred in the middle of the representative unit cell along both directions. The differences between the highest and lowest fibre strain for filling and perpendicular to filling directions are appeared to be constant for all strain levels, while in the difference between the highest and lowest fibre strain for the direction across the filling at higher strain levels (1.1%) appeared to be higher than its values for lower strain levels. The reason is believed to be due to the degree of change of the tow geometry at the tow edges is higher than its values in the middle of the unit cell.

Fig.16 3D plot for strain mapping at 0.5 % applied strain in Vectran plain weave composites

Fig.17 Contour micrograph for strain mapping at 0.5% applied strain in Vectran plain weave composites

3-2-2 Two dimensional (2D) strain distribution

Figs. 16 to 19 show the two dimensional distributions of local fibre strain obtained from the representative unit cell of the Vectran/epoxy plain weave lamina in the form of three dimensional plots and contour graphs at two levels of strain 0.5% and 1.1%. For all levels of applied strains the fibre strain decreases from the edge to almost the centre along both the filling and across the filling directions.

Fig.18 3D plot for strain mapping at 1.1 % applied strain in Vectran plain weave composites

Fig.19 Contour micrograph for strain mapping at 1.1% applied strain in Vectran plain weave composites

Referring to Fig. 5 the volume fraction in the middle of the defined unit cell is higher than its value at the edges of the unit cell and this leads to the high modulus and increases the strain at the edges of the unit cell, while at the middle of the unit cell the volume fraction increases and the modulus decreases, and the fibre strain decreases at the middle of the defined unit cell.

4- Conclusion

From the literature the key improvements of Vectran fibres include creep/relaxation, moisture regain, abrasion resistance and strength properties [4], but from the single fibre deformation we can add to the previous conclusions that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful tool to measure local fibre strain in case of Vectran fibers as well as many of high performance fibres such as Aramid fibres and PBO fibres. Also this could be extended to measure local fibre strain within the composite lamina under the conditions of using resins can be penetrated by a laser beam. The results also show that the strain induced band shift rate equal to $4.67 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain, and fibre modulus equal to 126 GPa with both stress and strain 3.9 GPa and 3.1 % respectively. The point to point strain distribution show that the strain increased around the edges of the representative unit cell, while the strain decreases almost at the centre of unit cell. The main reason governing the variation of strain along both directions filling and across the filling is the change of tow geometry due to the increase of the applied load. Further studies will be carried out to compare the pervious results with finite element models describing the stress or strain distributions caused by change of tow geometry.

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